

Conference Abstract

Population dynamics of two troglobitic *Troglophalurus* (Scorpiones: Buthidae) scorpions from Brazil

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Abstract

Population dynamics studies raise relevant data to understanding ecological aspects and natural history of species as well as better conservation strategies. Using two scorpions species, *Troglophalurus translucidus* Lourenço, Baptista & Giupponi, 2004 and *Troglophalurus lacrau* (Lourenço & Pinto-da-Rocha, 1997) from Chapada Diamantina, Bahia state, Brazil, we estimate populacional parameters through mark and recapture methodology, and Jolly-Seber estimator. In addition, data on both species as sexual ratio, reproductive biology, growth, longevity, feeding habitats, and seasonality were analyzed in the caves and afterwards compared to other scorpion species as well as other arachnids. We captured and marked 82 specimens of *T. translucidus* and 65 specimens of *T. lacrau*. Population estimates were 361 ± 199 individuals to *T. translucidus* and 333 ± 252 to *T. lacrau*. Population estimates were considered high for the troglobitic scorpions when compared to subterranean arachnids or even with epigeal species of scorpions. Both troglobitic scorpions featured remarkable differences in relation to epigeal scorpions as higher longevity, longer reproductive period, slower growth. Besides *T. translucidus* showed marked seasonality with populacional variations in rainy seasons in contrast to *T. lacrau* with populacional stability. Suppl. material 1

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Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Population dynamics of two troglobitic Troglorhopalurus Lourenço Baptista & Giupponi, 2004 (Scorpiones: Buthidae) scorpions from Brazil [doi](#)

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